

Woman in Customary Position in Kavery Nambisan's "The Hills of Angheri"

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The Indian culture which boasts of an ancient civilization was not gender biased in the ancient days but unfortunately it adopted patriarchy with the advent of foreign rulers. During that magnificent period women excelled and attained eminence in all fields and also gained reverence. Women are the underprivileged lot and do not get their owed. The social norms in the names of customs, traditions, economic factor and cultural constraints block their way to a full-fledged life. And to beat it all, they remain ignorant of their legal rights. The society is andocentric and does not give them full play to deal with their own lives but sets measures to their abilities. Women have almost accepted their secondary role by devaluing themselves and by looking upon men as their protectors instead of companions and this has resulted in their very low self-esteem which gets reflected in their dispositions.

Nalli, in Kavery Nambisan's The Hills of Angheri, being a village girl delimited by people steeped in the age old culture and traditional beliefs, tries hard to escape into a new world of modernity. Her choice of selecting medicine is not accepted by her family members and even by her relatives. Her father rejects her choice by telling that her health condition is poor to work for the sick people. He adds that it is quite impossible for her to strain in the field of medicine. He says, "Six years of study and then a life time of hard work. You aren't strong" (HA 30). Her relatives criticize her that higher education will spoil her personal life. They are of the view that she might have a chance to elope with somebody who would be unworthy of her and to the family. Her grandfather who is the preserver of the family tradition is completely against her medical education.

Nalli's father finally agrees to her request after a great wavering of mind and she joins the Medical College in Madras. There Nalli finds it very difficult to place herself among the freaks and moderns in the campus. A sense of inferiority complex engulfs her and to come out of it she changes her dress code, cuts her long hair and modifies her

speech. When she visits the village during vacation, everyone comments on her short hair and her changed style. It is her father's visit to the college makes her feel uneasy as she is about to leave for outing with her boyfriends.

Though she moulds herself to fit into the modern set up, she has her inner restrictions towards the change in life. She just wants to escape from the prevailing condition of her life but not to reframe anything. Her silence in the Government hospital against bribery, Jai's negligence towards their village and his involvement in earning more money induce a sense of frustration in her. But she is not very strong to act against any malpractice or she cannot voice out her view related to anything. She silently watches everything without reacting to it. Her in-built restrictions force her to keep silent. Her attitude of skipping the work spot shows her existential problem.

When Jai gets the medical seat, the entire village feels happy and considers that Jai is a gift to their village. Everyone thinks that Jai is worthy of getting the medical seat as he is the intelligent boy in the whole village. But when Nalli gets the medical seat, nobody including her relatives appreciates it. They consider that sending Nalli to medical college is a mere waste as it involves unnecessary expenditure on education which is quite unwanted for a girl. They are of the opinion that she will in no way be useful to the village and to the family as she will leave them in the name of marriage very soon. Therefore they discourage her from going to medical college but she remains stubborn in her decision and so her father has to bend to her wishes. He gets the application form with the condition that he will send her to the medical college only if she gets the seat on merit. She strives hard and gets the seat on merit and her father has no option at all and sends her to the medical college as per her desire.

Nalli has secret dreams for Jai and desires to settle down in the village to serve the people at Angheri. But she has never expressed her desire to anyone about her secret love for Jai. Whenever her parents and her sister insist on her marriage she silently gets away from the place. She convinces them that she does not like marital life but wants to establish herself as a doctor. Her stay with her sister in Mysore gives her a sense of unrest. She cannot be normal and shuts herself off from everyone at home. She wants to avoid talking to anyone and pretends that she is busy or in a gloomy mood. When her sister Sujju compels her to get into marital life she replies, "I'm quite happy not being married. I like being a doctor" (164). On her refusal, Sujju comments: "A few more years and no one will look at you. All this reading and learning that you want to do will frighten them away" (164). She further adds, "I have a husband and a family. I have status. Do you know what happens to women without a husband? I don't have to tell you..."(165).

Nalli becomes anxious and restless. She believes that her father will understand her but her father says that he is no longer proud of her. "Is it such a difficult thing I'm asking? We're not forcing a husband on you" (165). He plans for a meeting with eligible doctors to select a life partner for her. But she rejects it saying that she is not for marriage. Her father is fed up and declares, "You're my problem child!" He expresses his frustration as, "I expected the best from you, spent more on your education than Vishnu's and you repay me with ingratitude" (165). Though she has a strong desire to establish herself as a doctor and prove her ability as a surgeon and to serve the needy, from her heart of hearts she is unhappy with the way she leads her life. She finds that she doesn't fit herself to the environment of Mysore and the corruptive atmosphere of the city life. She feels a vague disquiet, resentment directed at everyone.

Nalli is strong in her ideas. Though everyone in the family forces her to settle down in life, she does not want to get married because she has already made her mind up after Jai's wedding. Belying her expectations, Jai has married another woman. But Nalli does not have any grudge against Jai. She remains a spinster and continues her relationship with Jai only for the purpose of constructing a hospital in Angheri. She visits Jai in Bombay and patiently waits for him to talk

about the plan of coming back to their village. She feels frustrated when she learns that Jai is unwilling to come back as he is after money and fame and has no concern for the villagers who are still expecting his service in the village. Nalli gets angry with the way Jai reacted but she is unable to retaliate and controls her emotions and feelings. She does not want to burst out as she thinks she has nothing to do with the life of Jai. As a modern doctor, she would have expressed her distaste in his decision and disloyalty towards his village. But the inborn silence and tolerance make her keep quiet and accept the fact as it is. She wants to build a hospital on her own in the village but the lack of interest and support from her relatives and neighbours pushes her aside. Nobody believes that she will do her best for the village and she too struggles to establish herself as a doctor like Saru in *The Dark Holds No Terrors* who establishes herself as a successful physician in the society. Saru's success results in misunderstanding in her marital life but in the case of Nalli she lacks confidence in her profession also. She tries to pull Jai to stand by her to serve the village. Normally a woman who is immersed in traditional ideas finds it very difficult to come out of the shell and prove her ability. Her traditionalism pulls her down from her level of confidence and she struggles a lot to come out of it. Kavery Nambisan presents even Nalli's mother as gifted with the power of determination. After the death of Nalli's father her mother's will power takes the family forward and makes the people in the family understand their responsibilities. There is nothing much relating to the traditional attitudes of female characters in the novel except Nalli's hesitation to get into her successful profession and marriage.

In the beginning of her career as a surgeon, she stands as a mute witness to the irregularities in her professional field at various places. Since she has been brought up in an oppressed atmosphere, she lacks confidence to encounter them. But in Madras she has grown in stamina to challenge the Chief of the hospital for commercialization of the service and commitment of irregularities. She even threatens to take the issue to the Health Minister but the intransigent authority indicts her for insubordination and shows her the way out. She learns that she does not have tangible evidence and the resources for engaging a lawyer to put up a fight and wakes up to the fact that she will have to fight a losing battle and leaves it. She finds it difficult to reconcile with the surroundings wherever she goes. The spirit in her to serve her village which is steeped in old culture is indomitable and she decides to liberate herself from the self-centered attitude of the city life. She makes a self-analysis of her life and reads her diary. To put it in her own words, "...my first entry, made when I was sixteen, full of impudent idealism" (390). Now she has developed a pragmatic approach to life.

Both Jai and Nalli are brought up in the same village and get the same education. Being a male, Jai has advantages over Nalli. Jai has improved financially and has name and fame to his credit but has lost peace in his family life. He has learnt to diagnose patients professionally whereas Nalli has grown in intellect to read people and situations. She rightly pinpoints that the problems in his family life are that his wife and parents needed him and not his money, success or status. She speaks with self confidence as, "In my own life, I had done what I wanted when it concerned big issues. Only in little things did I give in, let others decide" (387). Jai has hurt everyone whom he cares for in his life whereas Nalli has only sacrificed her life and has not hurt anyone.

Nalli is able to think in advance on her future when she says,

I could see myself ten, fifteen years ahead: stouter, calmer, more capable, known as such-and-such surgeon. Breast cancer? Go to her, she's good. Was I good? For how long would I continue to walk in and out of wards which smelt of fever, pain, humiliation and death? (390)

She could shrewdly calculate Jai's future as,

Twenty years from now the only difference would be more success, greying hair, spectacles maybe, and a paunch. He said he wanted a more restful practice but it would not happen....He was finished because he had stopped taking risks. (389)

But she does not lose the quality of facing adverse consequences boldly. Even at the beginning of her career she does not choose to lead a self-contented life with Jai discarding the village people who shun her. Instead she prefers to eschew Jai and live as a doctor in the village. After her experiences at various places she gains the inner strength to live for the people of her village who are not ready to acknowledge her modernity. Thus from a domesticated village girl she evolves into a forward-looking woman executing her plan assertively.

They do not look for a liberal life free from responsibilities; they desire only freedom from male centered exploitative activities. A progressive woman does not abominate ancestral bond but seeks acknowledgment for her emotional response and intellect. She solicits a positive response to her physical and emotional needs. Her battle is only against the antique values of the society and not against the society itself. It is due to her courage and resilience she comes to terms with interpersonal relationships, values them and asserts herself as an individual.

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